

METHODS OF STATE REGULATION AND MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN TRADE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19563016>

Abstract. The necessity of state regulation of foreign trade is linked to protecting the national economy, the efficient use of national resources, and ensuring economic security. Effective policy serves to protect national producers, increase national income, and stabilize the national economy. However, incorrect policy can lead to social problems and lagging economic development. This article closely examines the concept of foreign trade activity and discusses its role in foreign economic activity. Furthermore, along with the practice of regulating foreign trade activity, the principles, methods, and mechanisms of regulation, as well as the subjects of foreign trade activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their characteristics, constitute the main subject of the article.

Keywords: International trade policy, foreign economic activity, subjects of foreign trade activity, foreign trade, customs duty, quota, export, import, protectionism, free trade, state policy, subsidies, trade balance.

Introduction. The foreign trade policy of any state is an important component of the government's general economic direction, and in a narrower sense, it is one of the spheres of budget-tax activity related to regulating the volume, commodity composition, and geographical direction of export-import commodity flows. Since foreign trade policy is inextricably linked with the internal aspects of economic development, its main task is to create favorable external economic conditions necessary for expanded reproduction within the country and the increase of national wealth.

Free trade policy (or *freedom of trade* from the English *free trade*) appeared as a phenomenon of economic life in the second half of the 18th century. A. Smith's famous work "*The Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*" played a decisive role in its theoretical justification. The theory of free trade was developed and almost brought to perfection in the works of another English economist, D. Ricardo. D. Ricardo developed Adam Smith's ideas on the importance of free entrepreneurship under competitive conditions and the role of the state as the "night watchman" of society, entrusting the national economy to the dominance of the "invisible hand," i.e., the laws of market self-regulation.

Classic examples of free trade policy can be observed in the economies of the Anglo-Saxon countries in the second half of the 19th century, especially in Great Britain and its dominions (states that were officially independent but were part of Britain until 1947). By the present time, not a single country in the state's possession remains with the classic form of the free trade system. This is understandable in itself, considering the significant increase in the role of the state's authoritative organizations in regulation. However, elements of the free trade policy are still significant in the economic course of many countries, especially in developed and small countries in terms of territory and resources, for example, Singapore.

In economic theory, free trade is usually contrasted with the policy of protectionism (Eng. **protection** - protection, patronage), i.e., a system of economic and administrative measures implemented by the state to protect the national economy from the harmful effects of internal and external market principles. In its essence, protectionism has existed since the first states were formed. The principles of this policy were theoretically developed in the works of the American statesman A. Hamilton (end of the 18th century) and the famous German economist F. List (mid-19th century). However, protectionism as a series of practical measures reached its climax on our planet during the totalitarian regimes of the left (USSR) and right ("Third Reich" - Fascist Germany) political flows. In these countries, there was a state monopoly in the sphere of trade.

Incorrect foreign trade policy has led to increased unemployment in a number of countries. For example, as a result of the NAFTA agreement, hundreds of thousands of manufacturing jobs were lost in the USA. While NAFTA supporters claimed that this agreement would create new jobs in the USA, growing imports from Mexico and Canada destroyed more jobs in the USA than exports created. In 1993-1996, the increase in exports to Mexico created 158,171 jobs in the USA, while the increase in imports from Mexico reduced 385,834 jobs in the USA. In turn, the increase in exports to Canada created 244,309 jobs, while the increase in imports from Canada resulted in the loss of 411,481 jobs in the USA. Overall, imports from Mexico and Canada during this period caused the reduction of 797,315 jobs in the USA. Taking into account the jobs created due to export growth, the net job loss amounted to 394,835.

This situation was also observed in some European Union countries, including Greece and Portugal, where the unemployment rate increased significantly due to the financial crisis and trade deficits. Such situations intensify in countries where the trade balance is disturbed, as employment opportunities decrease due to economic crisis and incorrect trade policy.

In addition to the economic effects mentioned above, foreign trade can also affect the social environment. For this reason, the state attempts to eliminate this negative impact through regulating foreign trade. Foreign trade can negatively affect the social environment in the following directions:

First, the influx of foreign products can diminish the importance of national traditions and values, leading to their disappearance. Second, globalization and standardization replace local culture and customs with global standards, negatively affecting national identification and diversity. For example, in Kyrgyzstan, the national white "Kalpak" headgear is accepted as a symbol of cultural heritage and national self-awareness. At the same time, its high cost led to the market being occupied by hats made of artificial fabric brought from abroad. This caused very negative perceptions in public opinion.

Furthermore, the influx of cheap and large quantities of products can lead to the formation of a culture of consumerism, an increase in people's inclination toward material benefits, and a decline in moral values. Countries with strong economic and cultural influence can imbue their culture into other nations, disrupting national values. Similar problems can be observed in Uzbekistan. Weddings, family celebrations, and ceremonies have become an integral part of national customs and traditions. At the same time, a number of meaningless rites alien to our nation and newly invented "traditions" are being added, causing excessive expenses and damaging national values and customs.

In addition, some goods and services can increase social inequality and lead to fragmentation in society. The widespread distribution of foreign languages and education systems reduces the importance of local languages and education systems, which can lead to the younger generation drifting away from national heritage. To minimize these negative effects, states need to implement policies aimed at preserving national culture and moral values. In this regard, measures such as protecting cultural heritage, supporting national language and education systems, and protecting local producers are of great importance.

In addition to the above, to protect the environment, the state may restrict the import of environmentally hazardous products. Ecological standards and requirements are of great importance in foreign trade. They are implemented to protect the environment, ensure sustainability, protect consumers, increase the competitiveness of local producers, strengthen international cooperation, develop innovations and technologies, encourage economic growth, and increase social responsibility.

Ecological standards and requirements are aimed at reducing damage to the environment during the production of goods and services. These standards help reduce the pollution of air, water, and soil. Ecological requirements promote innovative production methods, ensuring the rational use of natural resources and their restoration. Protecting consumers is also an important aspect of ecological standards. They help control the quality of products and protect the health of consumers, for example, by ensuring products free from harmful chemicals. Overall, ecological standards and requirements in foreign trade help protect the environment, ensure sustainable development, and protect human health and safety. They ensure long-term ecological and economic benefits for states and producers.

Mechanisms of regulation in the republic of Uzbekistan. Above, we examined the necessity of state regulation of foreign trade. In evaluating the effectiveness of the state's policy, it is important to analyze the results obtained; therefore, a system of various indicators is used to evaluate the effectiveness of foreign trade policy.

The international trade policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan constitutes a fundamental and integral part of the country's economic policy. Like any other state, the Republic of Uzbekistan considers supporting the country's importers and exporters of goods and services, producers and consumers, and guaranteeing their activities as one of its most important goals. According to Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Foreign Economic Activity" adopted on May 26, 2000, the main tasks of the law are to ensure the economic security of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the implementation of international economic activity, protect the economic sovereignty and interests of the republic, and create conditions for the development and integration of the national economy.

The main tasks of the country in the field of international trade are to facilitate the competitiveness of local products in the process of production and supply of goods in the country's domestic market, ensure economic stability, and ensure that foreign producers do not harm the interests of local producers. The market also aims to assist local producers in producing products for export.

If we were to consider competition within the Republic of Uzbekistan at present, it would be impossible to consider the results of the measures taken as positive, and in some cases, management of activity based on monopoly by certain enterprises could be observed. The influence of the country on the implementation of international trade activity can be seen in the

volume, composition, and geographical location of its export-import operations. The Republic of Uzbekistan acts by adhering to the international legal rules and principles recognized by civilized states, integrating the country's economy into the world economy, and observing the rules of international treaties, customs unions, and other free economic zones in which Uzbekistan participates.

Mechanisms of state regulation of international trade activity:

1. Customs-tariff regulations (mechanisms for regulating international trade by applying customs payments to imported and exported goods);
2. Non-tariff regulation (mechanisms for regulating international trade by imposing restrictions on goods based on their quantity or other economic characteristics);
3. Regulation of international trade by implementing prohibitions and restrictions on services and results of intellectual activity;
4. Economic and administrative measures to promote international trade activity.

Examination procedures for contracts concluded by legal entities, financed from the state budget funds or loans (debts) attracted by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, or provided under its guarantee, where more than 50 percent of the authorized capital belongs to the government, and subjects not financed from their own currency assets, applied by the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, Investments and Trade.

From this day, the customs system in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been monitoring import contracts. Based on the Decree No. PF-5012 of April 13, 2017, by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures to further improve the system of regulation in the field of foreign trade," the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, Investments and Trade of Uzbekistan was transformed into the Ministry of Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan.

This decree was adopted to improve foreign trade relations, increase efficiency, liberalize foreign trade, strengthen exports, further improve the export promotion system, and establish long-term stable commercial relations between local manufacturing companies and their foreign partners. Uzbekistan is considered responsible for developing and implementing the country's foreign trade policy and coordinates the work of state bodies on regulating foreign trade activity.

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can confidently say that the policy of protectionism holds the primary place in Uzbekistan. We have always protected our internal trade subjects from international competition, and for this reason, our products may be expensive and may not meet quality standards compared to foreign ones. The other side of the matter is that monopolistic subjects occupy a firm position in our country.

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